

Chemistry part.

Day 1. SPION synthesis

Introduction

Solid Phase Extraction(SPE) is an invaluable tool in biology research because many biological objects have their interesting features in aqueous media, and other solvents are rather ... merciless to them.

DNA preparation, RNA preparation, even a lot of «immunoprecipitation» steps are, in their nature, SPE.

However, the way it is done is usually either lacking in ingenuity or cost efficiency — often both. I blame the black box nature of the widely available research tools and an effort to aestheticize science into a prohibitive area for «sharp minds» (often unsurprisingly homogeneous in certain important aspects) while simultaneously introducing corporate culture and office management to it, which are obviously detrimental for any research.

Possibly the best examples are «molecular biology kits», which are as widely used as they are intensely mystified, and almost all of which contain proprietary buffer formulations and an SP to E what you need with.

Solid Phase Extraction

Split into three types of solid matrix that can be a solid phase

Covalently crosslinked hydrophilic Gel Beads	Bulk porous matrices	Ultradisperse Functional Particles
Any separation type: cleared lysate centrifugation, magnetic separation, flow-through, including centrifuge-driven	Can only be used in flowthrough Columns, but achieve superb efficiency at that	Any separation type, however performs poorly in flowthrough columns
High dead volume, high nonspecific binding, has 27 kinds of Undocumented Behaviour for any use	Low dead volume, can be made lower at a price of higher hydrodynamic resistance (see HPLC)	Low dead volume, that diminishes relative to surface functional groups abundance as size and clumping goes down
Pore size is hard to adjust and harder to maintain at low-scale production i.e. a lab	Pore size is hard to measure, hard to maintain and hard to change	No pores because of inverted geometry
Cannot be used for efficient preparation of large complexes, including precipitin, as pore size drops with functional group maximum abundance	Cannot be used for efficient preparation of large complexes as the pore sizes decrease with	Can be used for efficient and arbitrarily multiplex preparation of precipitin complexes
Sigma M2 anti-Flag sepharose, Sephadex G-25 gel-filtration column	Silica spin columns, C18 columns for Schlenk, etc.	Pierce Streptavidin Magnetic Beads

Table 1. I am being biased and it allows me to do better than that one mule of Buridan's

Also I can make magnetic beads quite good, which also makes me biased for the third kind.

Superparamagnetic Magnetic Beads - Lack of Ambition is Bad, Actually

A lot of people tried to write a comprehensive assembly of magnetic beads preparation and use protocols, but the one most outstanding was written by Oberacker et al. in 2019 (<https://doi.org/ggc6jg> or <https://bomb.bio/>).

This one integrates use of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs), produced through rather simple procedure of iron oxide coprecipitation, coating with TEOS and subsequent use with optimized buffers. The optimization of buffers used still remains stellar outside of minor issues with clumping. Special thanks to the authors for Solid Web 1.0 website complete with phpBBS (albeit registration there is a mess).

However, the most critical piece of synthesis — stabilizing SPIONs in the intermediate steps - remains hard to reproduce, core particles are prone to random (and that's bad) aggregation, and generally desire to decay into rust too soon. And while the idea was really cool, and execution was nearly flawless, lack of maintenance (an ubiquitous disease in biology) soon played its role.

<https://bomb.bio/forums/topic/bomb-protocol-1-1-magnetic-core-nanoparticles-synthesis/page/3/#post-9424>

Fortunately, the very next year an improvement occurred through work of a collective of authors — Besenhard et al, late 2020 (<https://doi.org/gmws38>). In brief, aggregation occurs through irregular iron oxide precipitation at contact surfaces, welding core particles together. But irregular precipitation, unlike actual magnetite, remains susceptible to dissolution in citric acid. Once deaggregated, the samples can be stabilized using usual methods (oleic acid, for example).

Figure 1. And that's the reward, post-TEOS. Note that the target fraction can be easily separated through simply filtering it

The Recipe

We will need:

- 0.1 M HCl solution — approximately 200 ml;
- $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ powder — 4 g;
- FeCl_3 powder — 6,48 g;
- NaOH pellets — 40 g;
- good distilled water, or, if you don't trust your distiller, Type II water — 500 ml;
- few milliliters of saturated solution of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ or such;
- few milliliters of aqueous ammonia.

Figure 2. Safety is important, and these tacky food trays are perfect for mess management STEPS:

1. Preheat the water bath with a stirring plate underneath to 60°C.

Figure 3. *Sous vide* thermostat — biologists' best friend

2. While the bath is heating, dissolve iron chlorides in 0.1M HCl and aliquot, while filtering, into four(4) 50 ml centrifuge tubes, close tightly, put into -20°C to freeze.

3. Add 700 ml of water to 40g of NaOH in the stirring water bath (water-thermostated stirrer? Bucket.) Heat it up in the microwave to almost boiling, return to water bath. This gets rid of oxygen, which isn't good for redox-sensitive reactions. Drop some barium/magnesium/calcium hydroxide if you are afraid of carbonates.

4. Put some film that will stop you from sniffing ammonia or oxygen entering the reactor the whole time onto a 1L glass jar. There's probably merit to hot-sealing it airtight, but I find that rubber bands for money/Drosophila are sufficient. Pierce the film in a single spot once you are done and put the well-lubricated drip funnel into the hole.
5. Pump air away from iron solution, let it thaw, pour it into the drip funnel, close the drip funnel. Drip the contents slowly into the NaOH solution, Repeat for all four test tubes.

6. Add 10 ml 25% NH_3 (with a syringe, ammonia is foul smelling and somewhat toxic), keep it on stir for 20 minutes.
7. Magnetically decant the remaining solution with a magnet rated for at least 300kg, add 200 ml water, stir for 5 minutes — this is the wash step.

8. Wash with 200 ml water, 100 ml 1 M citric acid, let it be in airtight sealed container overnight. The next day wash it with deionized water and 96% ethanol

Day 2. Silica coating. Photocatalysed glutaraldehyde protection and subsequent chlorination.

Introduction

Silica coating is a fairly standard operation when dealing with MNPs – it provides both a lucrative platform for settling various functional groups on through silanization and protects SPIONs from oxidation. Usually silica coating is done through hydrolysis in presence of water. Once again, I start from bomb.bio protocols because they are relatively good.

Glutaraldehyde is a commonly used dialdehyde, no matter what your limitations on purchases are you can always make your own or precipitate it as sulfite adduct from common disinfecting agents. Usually this is not a molecule that you might remember in the first, second, or third echelon of compounds when talking about click chemistry, however click chemistry as a field continues growing and developing.

For example, if we look at the relatively recent article “General Dialdehyde Click Chemistry for Amine Bioconjugation” by Elahipanah et al., 2019, we can see that addition of second symmetrical aldehyde group removes the need for the extraneous reducing agents such as cyanoborohydride for stabilizing the chemical conjugate.

Glutaraldehyde, however, is not a stable compound, easily oxidated during chemical reactions, and many protection groups require sophisticated multi-solvent distillation steps. Instead, I chose to use the polymeric polyvinyl alcohol as a protection group and the accumulator of glutaraldehyde.

Out of concerns for availability, chlorination of the resulting glutaraldehyde-crosslinked PVA was done using DCC tablets.

The Recipe 1

We will need:

- hot 96% ethanol – 400ml;
- aqueous ammonia – 10 ml;
- TEOS – 9 ml;
- SPIONs – 4,5g (ethanol wet);
- Polypropylene 500ml flask;
- Magnetic stirrer with heating;
- Water bath set to 80°C

1. Add ammonia and SPIONs to the ethanol under fume hood and let them mix
2. Add TEOS and let them settle their differences for another 20-30 minutes
3. Add 75 ml water slowly and let the reaction proceed overnight.

The next day wash it with excess water and...

That's it! You made your batch of silica-coated MNPs that you can use for nucleic acid purification and more.

The Recipe 2

Photos are of a 2 times scaledown, forgive me.

We will need:

- 20g PVA
- 350 ml DMF
- Eosin Y
- DCC tablet (any)
- 10 ml concentrated glutaraldehyde
- lots of light
- funnel with filter paper

1. Dissolve PVA in 250ml hot (130°C) dry DMF, add Eosin Y, shake well, let the reaction mix, chill.

2. Add 10 ml concentrated glutaraldehyde, put on intense illumination for 2 hours. During that time white precipitate of glutaraldehyde-crosslinked PVA will start to form

3. Once precipitation is over, filter the precipitate, dissolve the DCC tablet in 100 ml DMF, add to the precipitate, incubate overnight at 80°C.

The next day wash it with excess ethanol.

Day 3. MNP silanization.

Introduction

Silanization is the process of modifying the silica surface with different functional groups fused to the silica “monomer”, usually alkoxyated silicon. Most common silanizing reagents include allyltriethoxysilane (ALTES), acquired through reacting TEOS with allylmagnesiumbromide Grignard reagent and aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES), ammonia addition derivative of ALTES.

Glutaraldehyde is not the only chlorinated product in the reaction, but as long as PVA remains insoluble due to, for example, presence of 80% ethanol, this is acceptable.

Aside from dialdehydes, you can modify amine moiety of APTES with, for example, acylating it with monochloroacetic acid, yielding IDA, which can be used in metal affinity purification, as reported by Kai Zeng et al., 2020 (doi:10/k648)

The Recipe

We will need:

- Magnetic beads in 80% ethanol;
- APTES, at the rate of approximately 1ml per 1g of water-wet beads;
- Glutaraldehyde+PVA chlorinated slurry OR sodium monochloroacetate pH 8 or 9;
- 80°C bath, magnetic stirrer

Put magnetic beads, APTES and modifier of choice into the bath, let it stir overnight, the next day wash with water, protect dialdehyde with bisulfite for storage and load Ni²⁺ for usage of Ni-IDA

Day 4. Testing the system.

Introduction

A lot of high-sensitivity quantitative reagents exist, one of them is fluorescamine, which is only fluorescent in presence of unreacted amines. Therefore, by progressively incubating small aliquots of BSA with known amount of magnetic beads, we can determine carrying capacity of them with rather high precision.

The Recipe

We will need:

- 50 mg/ml fluorescamine stock solution in acetone
- 0,2% = 2 mg/ml solution of BSA;
- 10 mg of dialdehyde modified MNPs;
- ultraviolet lamp

1. Add stepwise 500 microliters of BSA solution to dialdehyde MNPs, after a minute incubation magnetically separate and remove the liquid to 1.5 tube, add 10 microliters fluorescamine
2. Watch under ultraviolet, determine the carrying capacity of beads

Biology part.

Day 1. Cloning and insertion of alpha-tubulin into a pET plasmid

Well, the issue is that no good non-proprietary nanobody is published, which is bad and I want to solve it.

In order to immunize a system – regardless of it being a rabbit, a shark or cell-free – you need good expression of your target protein. Looking at the antibody catalogues, I noticed that anti-alpha-tubulin antibodies are common, while anti-beta-tubulin antibodies are pretty rare, so I decided to Not Tempt Fate and chose the alpha-tubulin gene on 84B of *Drosophila melanogaster*, with the following primers:

PRIMERS USED FOR THIS PART

NcoI_tuba-84	AAACCATggTgCgTgAATgTATCTCTATC
EagI_tuba-84	CggCCgTAgTACTCCTCAgCgCCCTCACC

Alpha-tubulin was amplified from total adult fly mRNA, so let's start here.

mRNA and cDNA preparation

Image 1. The materials.

54 fruit flies were flash frozen on dry ice and ground in a plastic microcentrifuge tube with a plastic pestle to avoid binding of nucleic acids to glass surfaces, and 500 microliters of homemade Tri-reagent were added and mixed with the pestle some more

HOMEMADE TRIZOL

8% Phenol (freshly distilled)

0,8 M Guanidinium Thiocyanate

0,4 M Ammonium Thiocyanate

0,1 M Sodium Acetate (in my experience, optional, but it's not the rarest reagent ever)

5 % Glycerol

Upon clearing at highest possible setting of centrifuge (~14kr_{cf} for 5') in a well-wrapped centrifuge tube (phenol is not nice to breathe; it degrades latex and nitrile gloves really fast and burns skin unpleasantly) 400 microliters TRizol was aspirated carefully (putting a 200microliter tip onto the 1000microliter tip helps), 108 microliters (sorry for superstitious readers, it wasn't intentional) of magnetic beads and 510 microliters of 96% ethanol were added, after which the tube was incubated at +4°C for 10 minutes, sometimes being flicked lightly. Magnetic beads were put on a rack and were allowed to settle

After a few(at least four, but I might have done five) washes with 20mM DTT 5 mM sodium citrate pH 6,4 buffered 80% ethanol (aka "RNA wash buffer") magnetic beads were dried under the RNase-free filter from a filter tip and resuspended in 50 microliters of DNaseI solution

DNaseI solution 100mL

2,5 mM MgCl₂ (=250 microliters of 1M stock)

0,5 mM CaCl₂ (=50 microliters of 1M stock)

10 mM Tris-HCl pH7,5 (=1mL of 1M stock)

DNase I (~5mg, I heat her with RNA storage buffer at 42°C during prep, so it isn't really RNase active at all)

After 5 minutes incubation at 37°C I inactivated DNase I and precipitated RNA with 2 volumes of Binding buffer (3M Gu-HCl, 10 mM Sodium citrate pH6,5, 85% ethanol), washed thrice with RNA wash buffer, dried the beads as above, added 50 microliters MashupRT buffer(big thanks to Alex Klenov for his MashupRT!):

MashupRT buffer 10× with 100 mg/L Mashup revertase

MashupRT buffer

250 mM Tris-HCl pH8,3 (odd, I know)

700 mM KCl

25 mM MgCl₂

62,5% Glycerol

0,1% NP-40

It doesn't freeze at -20°C and MashupRT does not immediately crash out in it.

Water, 10× Triphosphate Solution and the reverse primer were added, mixture was incubated for 30 seconds at 72°C, chilled immediately in ice, and then incubated for 40 minutes at 42°C (I don't believe in heating RNA too much).

PCR amplification

Image 2. Behold – a trinket!

Upon completion of the reaction, Taq polymerase (not a perfect buffer for Pfu-sso7d, and I was lazy) 100× and direct primer 200× (thank you Lumiprobe for shipping primers dry and at a nice

amount) were added and mixture was put into 10 thermocycler tubes for 30 cycles, annealing temp 53°C, elongation time 1 minute 30 seconds.

Once it was done (couple of hours), *EagI* and *NcoI* were added to pooled PCR reactions (they work well in this buffer without star activity), and mixture was incubated overnight alongside the reaction of 3 microliters of ~1g/l vector.

Day 2. Ligation and transformation of *E. coli*

Image 1. That one cloudiness in *E. coli* that everybody who *knows* knows, but nobody of those who don't *know* know what I am talking about

5 microliters of reaction was added for analysis of things going awry on a routine 1% agarose lithium borate gel with dsSafe stain. I use 3-lane gels cast on top of a coverslip, because a single one of them requires 2-3mL agarose, therefore saving quite a bit of it.

The rest of reaction was mixed with 500 microliters of binding buffer, washed 4 times with 80% ethanol, dried, and mixed with 20 microliters of 1× ligation buffer (I don't bother with purifying triphosphates, so it's the same stock solution. Beads were finally magnetically decanted without coming back. (Yes, all previous steps were the same beads)

p50-T4 ligase protein fusion (also thanks to Alex Klenow) was used for ligation, 5 units, 40 minutes at room temperature. Ligation mix was gently touched with a pipette tip lightly dipped in beta-mercaptoethanol (I don't know what everyone says, it improves efficiency a lot), and 100 microliters of the Transformation buffer (TB) was added.

200 microliters of overnight culture of DH5α cells (can be stored for a week at +4°C) was inoculated into 5 ml of LB medium and grown for a couple hours until it looks like in the image 1. After they are grown, 3ml of cells were spun down and resuspended in 1 ml of the Transformation buffer (TB)

The TB

+ kan, so the result is five stacks of gels which are not very parseable for people who aren't me, and that includes my sister so I removed that)

Day 4. Protein expression

Image 1. Using plastic bottles for protein expression is good for the bottom is ribbed and allows for efficient removal of CO₂, preventing acidification – CO₂ can be removed, acetic acid does not escape so easily. Sorry for different wonky workplace – I was visiting friends, so I came to them with the bottle of stuff.

BL21(DE3) colonies were washed from the plate with ice cold AIM into 400 ml AIM and shaken on RT in plastic bottle over the course of a workday and overnight.

Day 5. Inclusion bodies are good, sometimes

Image 1. Sometimes a centrifuge is chilled simply by being at the balcony.

Upon coming home, BL21(DE3) cells were harvested with usual diatomaceous earth - paper filter method, lysed with an improvised sonicator described above, centrifuged for 2 hours at the balcony to isolate inclusion bodies, and dissolved in 10 ml of standard, for me, inclusion body dissolving lysis buffer (20mM Tris-HCl pH7,5, 0,05% Triton X-100, 7,5M Urea, 10 mM DTT), which was subsequently cleared at max rpm for 5 hours.

Lysis buffer was mixed with 10 ml 20mM Tris-HCl and 500mg Ni-IDA magnetic nanoparticles and left overnight.

Day 6. Protein purification

Image 1. A lot of molecular biology is just illuminating yellow liquids

MNPs were washed with 5 ml 50mM imidazole 3 times – 3M urea, 1M urea and no urea in Tris-HCl pH 7,5, and eluted with 500 microliters 2M imidazole, subsequently diluted to 500mM after 1 minute incubation. MNPs were magnetically precipitated, and the solution was dissolved in 2 ml acetone pre-chilled to -20°C, powder was washed with ice cold 50% acetone thrice, with total yield of 40 milligrams of protein.

Protein was shown to be reasonably pure at the 10% acrylamide 200mM Tris-acetate 0,1% SDS denaturing gel with 65°C Tris-Acetate-Tricine running buffer at 300V (max setting of transformer), I used riboflavin for polymerization because it's a nice method, amidoblack 10B stain.

Image 2. The pitiful fruit of a biologists' labour – it isn't much, but it's honest work
Day 7-13. Cell-free reactions aka Pannings aka Groundhog Day
The PCR library for nanobodies was prepared from 20 test tubes of Gcons and 20 tubes of Lcons
plasmid from the original authors of the scaffold – see the scheme for yourself.

Image 1. Yes, it's 7 PCR reactions with total of 301 cycles. doi:10/jt8r

After pooling and 15 minutes of DpnI treatment (thank you *Bacillus subtilis* 168 secretion!), DNA was cleaned up using the aforementioned clean-up protocol on 100mg bare silica MNPs, and introduced into 7,5 ml of cell-free reaction mix. Reaction was run for 30 minutes, because yield is less important here. During that time, 20 mg dialdehyde MNPs (200 microliter slurry) was incubated with 10 mg alpha-tubulin (slightly less than batch carrying capacity, 10 mM MES pH5,8), and then reaction was quenched with 50 microliters 0,5% hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

After that tubulin-modified nanoparticles were added to the reaction mix, and, after 15 minutes incubation at +10°C water bath, cell-free mixture was decanted to react further for 5 hours in first panning, and discarded in next.

Nanoparticles were washed with 150mM NaCl in 10mM Tris-HCl pH7,5 in first two pannings, and with 200, 250 and 300 mM in three subsequent ones.

After that, ribosome-mRNA-protein complexes were denatured with 7,5 ml 6M guanidinium chloride, and the tubulin beads recycled.

2ml 1% silica-coated bead slurry in RNA Storage were added alongside 15 mL ethanol, and RNA was purified and RT-PCR similar to the prep above, except 10 microliters 0,5mM MnCl₂ was supplemented.

Final candidate was chosen by cutting out the most beautiful band in the densest region of 30% PAAG gel electrophoresis of the final panning and forgetting about it for two days due to the black mold incident.

Day 14. Cloning.

The excised band was frozen, ground in a test tube and purified according to the already described cleanup routine. Due to fears of poor DNA integrity, I decided to use Sebastian's good TSS protocol for transforming *E. coli* and utilize the power of blue-white selection – I used existing SmaI cut of pBluescriptSK(+) and ligated it with the DNA from PAAG band, then I added in 20 microliters ligation mix to cells in a TSS buffer

TSS buffer

10% PEG-6000

30 mM MnCl₂

5% ml DMSO

10 mM PIPES-KOH pH 6,7

0,1% beta-mercaptoethanol

LB to volume

Day 15. A single white colony

Day 16. A single plasmid prep

Day 17. Liquid LB transformation of BL21(DE3) and subsequent rocket electrophoresis of crude lysate

If you have a lot of plasmid and it wasn't stored long sometimes it makes sense to transform 1 ml of transformation buffer worth of competent cells and directly dump it to grow.

This is exactly what I did, and then I induced cells with Lactose and let grow until completely cloudy.

Sonicated cells I mixed with 1% agarose in 10mM Tricine-HCl pH8,2 and added 100 microgram, 20 microgram and 4 microgram tubulin.

All three "rockets" were too heavy to lift off, meaning that the resulting nanobody is not completely horrible.

Miscellaneous.

Day 1-3. Making agarose

1. Wash 50g IT-900+ agar suspension with excess of 65°C distilled water with 2mM sodium citrate 2 times for 5 minutes
2. Wash it with excess 65°C distilled water 3 times for 5 minutes
3. Wash it with excess 65°C ultrapure water 3 times for 5 minutes
4. Dry at 65°C overnight
5. Dissolve in 350 ml 105°C ethylene glycol
6. Cool to 85°C, add 150 ml 85°C isopropyl alcohol
7. Let precipitate overnight
8. Decant ethylene glycol/isopropyl alcohol, cut the slab of agarose into cubes
9. Wash cubes with 500 ml 85°C distilled water 3 times for 1 hour
10. Wash cubes with 500 ml 85°C ultrapure water 3 times for 1 hour
11. Dry at 65°C overnight

Day 1-3. Making triphosphates without charcoal (seems to be cleaner than charcoal method)

1. Grow 100-200 ml overnight culture of DH5alpha
2. Harvest cells onto filter paper, wash with dH₂O
3. Put cells – on filter paper – into 20 ml 1M formic acid in 60% methanol pre-chilled to -20°C
4. Extract overnight
5. Remove filter paper with cells, clear the solution if the filter broke, evaporate the methanol with vacuum pump while on -20°C ice bath
6. Resuspend residue in 1,2 ml 3M ammonium formate pH 6,4, freeze to -20°C
7. Lyophilize in a pre-weighed 1,5 ml microcentrifuge tube at -20°C ice bath
8. Sublimate excess ammonium formate away at +4°C in a large vacuum jar overnight (sometimes takes longer)
9. Dissolve triphosphates, aliquot, save one aliquot for measuring and TLC

Day 1-3. Making drosophila cell-culture suitable yeast extract

1. Get 100g yeast bricks, press them through sieve, put in paper towel
2. Dry in vacuum over freshly dried silica overnight
3. Mortar and pestle it into a fine powder, add 5 volumes distilled water (i.e. 2,5 liters per 5 bricks)
4. Incubate at 30°C until bubbling stops (usually couple hours)
5. Add 10mL 1% pronase solution
6. Incubate at 30°C for couple more hours, boil for 30 minutes to inactivate proteases
7. Filter the solution, reduce under vacuum
8. Spray dry the solution